

PROJECT DETAILS

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Summary

This report explains the methodology used to generate the deliverables D3.1 and D3.2, as well as the key attributes, their strengths, and their limitations. The deliverables D3.1 and D3.2 are part of Work Package 3, which aims to generate annual forest disturbance products covering the Iberian Peninsula and the Balearic Islands using time series data from Landsat (D3.1) and Sentinel-2 (D3.2).

The products generated by Agresta will be referred as the "Internal Dataset" to distinguish them from the three external products (Global Forest Change, European Forest Disturbance Atlas, and Alert and Annual Changes System). All these products will be harmonized in Work Package 4 and in Work Package 5, all products will undergo validation.

This work has been built upon a previous project that implemented change detection based on Landsat time series in three pilot provinces of the Iberian Peninsula. That project was conducted within the framework of the Bosques 3.0 Operational Group, with the goal of improving the certification audit process for sustainable forest management under the PEFC certification body.

The current challenge was twofold: not only did the methodology need to transition from Landsat to Sentinel-2, but the project also needed to scale up from a provincial to a national level. This involved assigning the remaining provinces to one of the three change detection models developed during the pilot phase.

As part of WP3, two key deliverables are provided. Mapping products were generated using time series of satellite imagery analyzed with the Continuous Change Detection and Classification (CCDC) algorithm. In the first phase, areas of forest loss were identified, followed by the classification of changes into four categories: clear-cutting, thinning, bush clearing, and wildfires. The final maps were produced on an annual basis.

- **D3.1:** Change Products derived from Landsat imagery
- **D3.2:** Change Products derived from Sentinel-2 imagery

For Landsat, a total of 12 annual mosaics have been delivered, covering the period from 2018 to 2023. These include:

- 6 mosaics for **Change vs. No Change**
- 6 mosaics for **Type of Change**

For Sentinel-2, eight annual mosaics have been provided for the period from 2020 to 2023. These include:

- 4 mosaics for **Change vs. No Change**
- 4 mosaics for **Type of Change**

The mosaics can be accessed through the following [link](#).

1.1 Key Attributes of Internal Datasets

The following table summarizes the main characteristics of each dataset, facilitating their comparative evaluation and integration into the project's forest disturbance analysis framework. Detailed methodological aspects are included in Appendix I.

Internal Products	Landsat and Sentinel-2
Temporal Coverage	Landsat: 2018 – 2023 (with the possibility of extending to years prior to 2018, as well as 2024 and the first quarter of 2025) Sentinel-2: 2020 - 2023
Spatial Coverage	Iberian Peninsula and the Balearic Islands
Temporal Resolution	Annual (loss)
Disturbance Types	clear-cutting, thinning, shrubs clearing, and wildfires.
Multiple Disturbance Events per Pixel	No
Input Data Used	Landsat (30m) and Sentinel-2 (20m), respectively
Algorithm Used for Classification	Continuous Change Detection and Classification + Random Forest
Validation Data	Photo-interpretation of points obtained through stratified and random sampling.
Accuracy	Landsat: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Change detection overall accuracy: 92%. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> o user's accuracy change class: 61% - 88%; o producer's accuracy change class: 85% - 99%. - Type of change overall accuracy: 70% Sentinel-2: to be validated within the RIGORMED project in WP5
MMU	Landsat: 5 pixels (0.45 ha, Landsat pixel) Sentinel-2: 12 pixels (0.48 ha, Landsat pixel)
Reference System (EPSG)	EPSG:4326 (WGS 84)
Output Details	Type of change each year
Open Access	NA
Mask Used (forest/non-forest)	Forest <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - MMU of 0.5 hectares - 10% tree cover density threshold

1.2 Strengths and Limitations of Internal datasets

1.2.1 Strengths

- Utilizes satellite-based observations for standardized and consistent monitoring.
- Automated workflows enhance scalability and reproducibility.
- High-resolution mapping with Landsat (30m) and Sentinel-2 (20m) for national-scale assessments.
- The implementation is optimized for detecting changes in 6-month intervals. However, in this case, mapping has been produced annually, covering up to 2023, as the external products used for comparison are only available on a yearly basis until that year. Nevertheless, more frequent updates—such as monthly changes over the past six months—could be generated if needed.
- Implemented methodology enables national-scale vegetation loss mapping.
- High overall accuracy in detecting change (Loss)/no change, with additional classification into four specific disturbance types: clear-cuts, thinning, shrubs clearing, and forest fires.
- Specifically tailored to Spanish forests.
- Due to the algorithm's ability to utilize all available observations from a time series, data changes can be detected earlier than with other methods. Additionally, the higher frequency of Sentinel-2 imagery allows for even earlier detection of changes compared to Landsat.

1.2.2 Limitations

- There are challenges in accurately detecting changes in sparse vegetation and semi-arid ecosystems, leading to commission errors in disturbance detection. Especially, major commission errors have been identified in those years when drought conditions were extreme. The algorithm detects a decline that was not identified during the photointerpretation of very high-resolution images.
- The classification system is limited to four disturbance types, meaning changes caused by factors outside these categories may be misclassified.
- The methodology is not specifically optimized for detecting subtle disturbances, though it occasionally captures such changes.
- Currently, the approach focuses solely on vegetation loss and does not account for vegetation recovery or regrowth.
- Persistent cloud cover poses a significant issue for all datasets, especially in humid and mountainous Mediterranean regions, affecting disturbance detection and classification reliability.
- The cartography derived from Sentinel-2 remains insufficiently tested, both in terms of "Change-No Change" detection and "Type of Change" classification. A more comprehensive validation is required to fully assess its performance.

- Preliminary visual analysis suggests that commission errors may be higher in the Sentinel-2 derived product; however, the evaluation in Work Package 5 will provide more detailed insights into this matter.
- Change classification models can be improved in two ways: by enhancing the accuracy of detecting different types of changes and by increasing the number of classes in the classification.
- Considering that the models were developed for Landsat, applying them to Sentinel-2 has yielded results that require improvement.

2 Methodology

The national-scale change detection mapping for the 2018–2023 period was built upon a methodology developed and tested in a previous project. Initial validation was conducted for the years 2017–2021 in three provinces, focusing on binary change/no-change classification. Subsequently, the approach was refined and tested for change type classification using 2022 data.

Although the timeframes differ slightly, the underlying methodology remains consistent and has been adapted and expanded for nationwide application across the full 2018–2023 period. It is worth noting that for Sentinel-2 data, the effective national-scale change mapping was carried out for the 2020–2023 period only, as several years of training data were required prior to application. Additionally, although Sentinel-2 was launched in 2015, early years posed limitations in terms of consistent data availability, influencing the selection of the operational period.

2.1 Forest Definition

To define the Forest Mask for change detection, we used the Forest Type 2018 dataset, a high-resolution raster layer with a 10-meter spatial resolution from the Copernicus Land Monitoring Service. This dataset classifies land into three categories: non-forest areas, broadleaved forests, and coniferous forests, following the FAO's forest definition. It applies a minimum mapping unit (MMU) of 0.5 hectares and a 10% tree cover density threshold, excluding tree-covered areas in agricultural and urban contexts. From this dataset, we simplified the classification into two categories: "Forest" and "No Forest."

2.2 Platform Selection

The project's methodology is based on the use of the Google Earth Engine (GEE) platform (Gorelick et al., 2017), which was selected after evaluating various cloud processing solutions. GEE is a tool that enables the analysis and visualization of geospatial data at a global scale, leveraging Google's computing infrastructure. It provides access to a vast repository of geospatial data, including Landsat and Sentinel satellite imagery, and offers an API compatible with both JavaScript and Python for interactive development. However, the platform does have some processing limitations, which required us to optimize both the code and the algorithm's parameters.

2.3 Continuous Change Detection and Classification (CCDC) Algorithm

In recent years, several algorithms have been developed for change detection using satellite image time series, such as BFAST (Breaks for Additive Seasonal and Trend), LandTrendR (Landsat-based detection of Trends in Disturbance and Recovery), and CCDC (Continuous Change Detection and Classification) (Cai et al., 2022). Among these, we chose the CCDC algorithm due to its ability to detect changes continuously.

Another key feature of CCDC is its capacity for near-real-time data processing, making it ideal for detecting and classifying recent changes. It generates change maps that not only detect the occurrence of changes but also classify them into different categories. This makes it particularly suited for applications such as forest monitoring, providing accurate and up-to-date information based on satellite time series data. Additionally, its implementation in GEE (Arévalo et al., 2020) provided a robust platform with efficient processing times.

The CCDC algorithm (Zhu & Woodcock, 2014) is designed for analyzing satellite image time series to detect land cover changes continuously and accurately. The method uses multitemporal harmonic models that fit a periodic function to each pixel in the images. The model combines linear and harmonic terms to capture seasonal patterns and long-term trends in the data. A notable strength of the model is its ability to adapt to natural variations in the signal, such as seasonality or noise, allowing it to identify only significant changes that deviate from the expected pattern (Zhu & Woodcock, 2014).

The initial model fitting uses the first twelve cloud-free, shadow-free, and snow-free observations, which are masked using the Fmask method (Zhu & Woodcock, 2012), and analyzes the following three to detect changes in the pixel's behavior. This temporal grouping helps mitigate ephemeral effects, such as noise or temporary anomalies (e.g., dense aerosols, smoke, or flooding), which could be mistaken for land cover changes. A real change is considered only if the three consecutive observations fall outside the predicted range. The change threshold varies depending on the disturbance type and is adapted for each pixel using all bands. The least squares method calculates the Root Mean Square Error (RMSE) for each band, and the observations are compared with the model within a range of $\pm 3 \times \text{RMSE}$. If the three cloud-free observations fall outside this range, a change in the land cover is detected (Zhu & Woodcock, 2014). This method allows for the generation of change maps and associates the detection of the change with a specific date (Pasquarella et al., 2022).

Another important feature of this algorithm is its ability to process multiple spectral indices simultaneously for change detection. This is a significant advantage, as it allows for better detection of different types of changes.

Figure 1. Workflow of the change detection process using the CCDC algorithm

Previous studies have recommended using three consecutive observations to classify a pixel as a "change" (Zhu & Woodcock, 2014). However, when applying this value in our study area, we observed an increase in false positives, highlighting the need for specific adjustments to improve the algorithm's accuracy in particular contexts.

2.4 Data collection and pre-processing

2.4.1 Landsat imagery

For the construction of the Landsat time series, we used images from Landsat 5, 7, 8, and 9 with Level-2 processing from Collection 2 and Tier 1. These images are ortho-rectified and atmospherically corrected, providing Surface Reflectance data. They include three bands in the visible spectrum (RGB), one in the near-infrared (NIR), and two in the shortwave infrared (SWIR).

Image selection was performed retrospectively. That is; to identify changes for 2020, we built the time series using images from the previous 20 years and all available images after 2020. Once the Landsat time series was constructed, we removed pixels affected by clouds, haze, shadows, as well as saturated pixels and those influenced by the presence of aerosols. This was done using three specific bands included in the Landsat data: QA_PIXEL, QA_RADSAT, and SR_QA_AEROSOL.

The QA_PIXEL band contains quality statistics collected from the image data and cloud mask information for each scene, used to identify pixels affected by clouds, fog, shadows, etc. The QA_RADSAT band helps identify saturated pixels, while the SR_QA_AEROSOL band, available only in Landsat 8 and 9, is used to mask pixels affected by aerosols, as they can degrade image quality. After masking the poor-quality pixels, we calculated a series of spectral indices (SIs) for each image in the time series. These indices help enhance subsequent analyses by highlighting specific spectral information contained in the image bands.

2.4.2 Sentinel-2 imagery

Sentinel-2 images are a series of medium-resolution multispectral images captured by the Sentinel-2 mission of the European Union's Copernicus program. This constellation consists of two satellites equipped with sensors capable of capturing images across 13 spectral bands. In our application, we use 10 of these bands, ranging from the blue spectrum to the short-wave infrared (SWIR). Each spectral band allows us to observe specific characteristics of the Earth's surface, including vegetation, water bodies, crops, soil, and snow cover, among others.

Sentinel-2 offers a spatial resolution of 10 meters for the visible and near-infrared (NIR) bands and 20 meters for the remaining bands. Compared to Landsat imagery, Sentinel-2's higher resolution allows for the detection of finer-scale changes. Additionally, its higher acquisition frequency results in a greater number of available images for the same time period.

The Sentinel-2 image processing workflow follows a similar approach to the one implemented for Landsat and has also been developed on the Google Earth Engine (GEE) platform. The workflow begins with the selection of harmonized images at processing level 2A, acquired within the analysis period (from March 28, 2017, to the present). These images provide surface reflectance values and have undergone radiometric calibration, atmospheric correction, and geometric correction.

Once the images are selected, cloud and shadow pixels are removed. In addition to the 2A images, two additional datasets available in GEE are required: the Sentinel-2 Level-1C image collection and cloud probability images.

To create the cloud mask, we use bands B7, B8, B8A, and B10 from the Sentinel-2 Level-1C product. These bands are used to compute the Cloud Displacement Index (CDI), which is essential for determining shadow locations. Finally, we combine this information with the cloud probability layer to identify clouds, transform directional distance, project cloud shadows onto the image, and mask unwanted pixels. After masking clouds and shadows, we calculate the same spectral indices (SI) obtained for Landsat, using the equivalent Sentinel-2 bands.

2.5 Reference Database for Quality Assessment

2.5.1 Change - No Change Database

To assess the "Change" – "No Change" cartography across the three pilot provinces, a comprehensive reference database was developed. The selection of the 2017–2021 period was driven by the availability of very high-resolution (VHR) imagery, which is essential for accurate change validation through photointerpretation. Validation points were collected using a stratified random sampling strategy, with strata defined by the Landsat map classes. Each selected point was then subjected to photointerpretation using VHR imagery and classified into the appropriate category. Beyond quality assessment, this database played a crucial role in establishing the thresholds for significant change magnitudes, as described in section 2.6.1.

2.5.2 Type of Change Database

A different methodology was used to create the reference database for validating cartography based on the type of change. For each pilot province, changes recorded in 2022 by the Global Forest Change (GFC) product (Hansen et al., 2013) were utilized. Between 150 and 300 polygons per province were randomly selected, focusing only on those with an area of 0.4 hectares or more. The number of polygons that were photointerpreted using VHR imagery depended on the availability of suitable imagery to assess changes occurring specifically in 2022.

A supplementary point reference database was generated for 2022, extending beyond the pilot provinces, to evaluate the national-level scalability of the cartography. This database focused on assessing the accuracy of both the change-type and change-no-change cartographies in these expanded regions. Validation points were collected using a stratified random sampling methodology, with strata defined by the five classification categories: "No Change," "Clear-Cut," "Thinning," "Shrubs Clearing," and "Wildfire." It should be noted that "Clear-Cut," as used here, indicates a reduction in tree cover density, though determining the exact percentage of reduction remains difficult.

These points were selected from the Landsat-derived cartography and subsequently photointerpreted using VHR imagery, assigning each point to its corresponding category. The same point set, derived from the Landsat cartography, was also employed for validating the Sentinel-2 cartography.

Figure 2. Examples of forest disturbances identified in the cartography

2.6 Development of Cartographic Products

The methodology (Figure 3) is divided into two main phases. First, **change detection** is performed, resulting in an intermediate map of "Change" vs. "No Change" within the analyzed time period. In the second phase, the **type of change** is classified by combining the predictor variables derived in the previous step and applying the Random Forest algorithm (Breiman, 2001).

Figure 3. Methodological workflow

Before proceeding, it is important to clarify that, for the generation of both the **Change–No Change cartography** and the **cartography by change type**, the methodology and configuration parameters of the CCDC algorithm were initially defined for Landsat. Once the two Landsat-derived cartographies were validated, the same methodology was applied to Sentinel-2. The differences between the two methodologies are minimal. After initial testing, it was decided to keep most of the configuration parameters unchanged, including the threshold for filtering out

insignificant changes, the spectral indices used for change detection, and even the Random Forest models. This information will be extended in the following sections.

The following section first focuses on the cartography generation process using Landsat, followed by Sentinel-2, highlighting only the key differences observed during the cartography generation process.

2.6.1 Landsat

2.6.1.1 Change – No Change Maps (2017 – 2021)

The change detection process begins with selecting satellite imagery that has undergone radiometric calibration, atmospheric correction, and geometric correction to ensure accurate surface reflectance values. Before applying the CCDC algorithm, which includes its own method for removing clouds, shadows, and snow, an initial filtering step is conducted to eliminate pixels affected by clouds, haze, shadows, saturation, or aerosols. A long time series of satellite images was used, covering the period from 1997 to the present. However, **the change detection analysis specifically focused on the period between 2017 and 2021**, allowing for quality assessment of the resulting cartography using very high-resolution imagery.

Next, various spectral indices were calculated for each image in the time series. The selection of spectral bands for analysis was based on two key factors: minimizing the number of bands to optimize processing speed in Google Earth Engine (GEE) and prioritizing bands that previous studies have shown to be effective in detecting forest-related changes. Based on this analysis, three main indices were chosen: **Normalized Burn Ratio (NBR), Tasseled Cap Wetness (Wetness), and Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI)** (Kennedy et al., 2010; Grogan et al., 2015).

Once the vegetation indices time series were generated, CCDC was applied to detect changes within the defined period. One of the algorithm's direct outputs is the magnitude of change, where negative index values indicate vegetation loss (Bradley, 1997).

For the province of Asturias, all three vegetation indices were used to generate the change map. The change magnitude was defined as the sum of the magnitudes of change for each index. For the other two provinces, only one spectral index was used, as combining multiple indices significantly increased the false positive rate. False positives are more common in open forested areas, where variations in soil moisture can cause changes to be detected that do not reflect real changes. This phenomenon was especially common in the province of Sevilla, where severe drought periods resulted in changes that introduced noise into the resulting map.

To identify only the changes relevant to the project, an optimal change magnitude threshold was determined using a Receiver Operating Characteristic (ROC) curve. Pixels with values exceeding this threshold were classified as "No Change."

The **ROC curve** is a graphical representation of a classifier's performance across different threshold values. It plots the **True Positive Rate (TPR)** against the **False Positive Rate (FPR)** to illustrate the trade-off between sensitivity and specificity. In the context of threshold selection for classification, the

ROC curve helps determine the optimal value by balancing the detection of true positives while minimizing false positives. The **area under the ROC curve (AUC)** quantifies the classifier's overall performance, with higher values indicating better discriminative ability. To calculate the magnitude thresholds using the ROC curve, we relied on the photointerpreted points described in **Section 2.5.1**.

Due to the differing forest characteristics across the three pilot provinces, it was necessary not only to use distinct spectral indices and magnitude thresholds but also to configure specific algorithm parameters for each province. **Table 1** presents the configuration parameter values for each case. The **Number of Observations (#Obs)** represents the minimum number of consecutive observations required to confirm a change. The **Chi-Square Probability** value controls the algorithm's sensitivity to detecting changes, while the **Min Num of Years** parameter defines the minimum time interval, in years, before the model is reevaluated. Finally, **Lambda** regulates the degree of model simplification when fitting temporal data, striking a balance between capturing real changes and avoiding overfitting to minor fluctuations or noise.

Table 1. Algorithm Configuration Parameters for Pilot Provinces

Province	Index	Change Magnitude Threshold	#Obs	Chi Square Probability	Min Num of Years	Lambda
Asturias	NDVI TCW NBR	-2673	6	0.99	1.33	0.002
Huesca	TCW	-141	9			
Sevilla	NBR	-131	12			

2.6.1.2 Type of Change Maps (2022)

In the **second phase** of the analysis, **change types were classified into four categories**: "Clear-Cut", "Thinning", "Shrubs Clearing", and "Wildfire". For each pixel identified as "Change", a set of predictor variables was generated. These included the magnitude of change of the indices used for detection, as well as reflectance values from the Green and SWIR-2 bands before and after the change. These values were obtained by generating synthetic images at the start and end of the analyzed period, estimated from the adjusted harmonic model (Arévalo et al., 2020). Additionally, coefficients associated with the harmonic regression models were also considered. In the case of Asturias, in addition to the change magnitudes from the three spectral indices, the sum of these magnitudes was included as an additional variable.

Once the predictor variable stack was selected, a Random Forest classification model was used to identify the change type. Given the significant variation in forest conditions between the three pilot provinces, independent models were developed for each one. This strategy allowed for model adjustments specific to each forest reality and improved classification accuracy.

Training areas for classification were based on the initial "Change" vs "No Change" map obtained for the 2017-2021 period. To expand the training sample for change types, training areas were defined in both the pilot provinces and other associated provinces, selected for their similar forest characteristics or to balance the presence of all classes in the training sample. The delineation

and assignment of change type to each training area were performed through photointerpretation of very high-resolution images obtained from the National Aerial Orthophotography Plan (PNOA) and Google Earth. Table 2 presents the provinces where training areas were defined and their relationship to the pilot provinces.

From these training areas, a preliminary model was adjusted using the Random Forest algorithm to identify the most relevant predictor variables. With the selected variables, the final model was built using Random Forest again, optimizing its predictive capacity.

Finally, the models were trained using data from the 2017–2021 period, with prediction and quality assessment conducted for 2022. This process resulted in a classified change map for the three pilot provinces in 2022.

The model developed for Asturias was named the "Northern Model," the one for Huesca the "Northeastern Model," and the model for Sevilla the "Southern Model."

Table 2. Training Areas and Key Predictor Variables

Province	Training Areas	Key Predictor Variables (*)
Asturias	Pontevedra, Asturias	WETNESS_MAG, NBR_MAG, GREEN_start, WETNESS_COS, SWIR2_end, GREEN_end, SWIR2_start, NDVI_SIN, NDVI_MAG, NDVI_COS, MAG_sum, NBR_COS, NBR_SIN
Huesca	Huesca, Navarra, Barcelona	SWIR2_end, WETNESS_COS, GREEN_start, SWIR2_start, GREEN_end, WETNESS_INTP, WETNESS_RMSE, WETNESS_SIN, WETNESS_MAG
Sevilla	Sevilla, Badajoz, Alicante, Castellón	NBR_MAG, NBR_SIN, NBR_COS, NBR_COS2, SWIR2_start, NBR_SIN2, GREEN_start, NBR_RMSE, SWIR2_end, NBR_INTP, GREEN_end

(*) *_MAG*: refers to the magnitude of each index, *_sum*: to the sum of the magnitudes of different indices, *_start*: to the band value at the beginning of the period, *_end*: to the band value at the end of the period, *_COS*, *_SIN*, *_INTP*: to the coefficients of the adjusted harmonic model before the change, *_RMSE*: root mean square error of the adjusted model.

2.6.1.3 Scaling to the National Level

To scale up from the three pilot provinces to a national level, each province was assigned to one of the three existing models, considering both the local forestry practices and the landscape characteristics. In some cases, multiple models were tested for a given province, and the one that produced the best results was selected.

To evaluate model performance, a stratified random sample of points was collected and analyzed through photointerpretation (described in section 2.5.2). A confusion matrix was then used to compare the mapped values with observed data at each point, allowing us to calculate overall accuracy.

This analysis led to the introduction of two additional models, as the original pilot province models did not yield satisfactory results for certain regions. The configuration parameters for change detection in these new models, named the "Central Model" and the "Eastern Model," are presented in Table 3. Table 4 provides an overview of the predictor variables used for type of change classification.

Table 3. Algorithm Configuration Parameters for the New Models

Model	Index	Change Magnitude Threshold	#Obs	Chi Square Probability	Min Num of Years	Lambda
Central	NDVI	-743	6	0.99	1.33	0.002
Eastern	NBR	-131	6			

Table 4. Training Areas and Key Predictor Variables for the New Models

Model	Training Areas	Key Predictor Variables (*)
Central	Segovia, Palencia, Salamanca	NDVI_COS,SWIR2_end,NDVI_SIN,SWIR2_start,GREEN_end, GREEN_start,NDVI_INTP,NDVI_SIN2,NDVI_COS2,NDVI_RMSE
Eastern	Barcelona, Castellón, Alicante	NBR_SIN,SWIR2_start,NBR_COS,GREEN_end,GREEN_start,SWIR2_end,NBR_SIN2,NBR_INTP,NBR_COS2,NBR_MAG

(*) _MAG: refers to the magnitude of each index, _sum: to the sum of the magnitudes of different indices, _start: to the band value at the beginning of the period, _end: to the band value at the end of the period, _COS, _SIN, _INTP: to the coefficients of the adjusted harmonic model before the change, _RMSE: root mean square error of the adjusted model.

Figure 4. Final allocation of provinces across the five models.

2.6.2 Sentinel-2

As stated earlier in **Section 2.6**, the methodology implemented for **Sentinel-2** is identical to the one used for change mapping with **Landsat**.

Following the same approach as in the **Landsat-based methodology**, a set of spectral indices was generated. Drawing from the Landsat experience, the same three key indices were selected: **Normalized Burn Ratio (NBR)**, **Tasseled Cap Wetness (Wetness)**, and **Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI)**.

The differences between the two methodologies are minimal, mainly involving adjustments to the **number of observations** required to confirm a change. After initial testing, other configuration parameters were kept unchanged, including the **threshold for filtering out insignificant changes**, **the spectral indices used for change detection**, and **the Random Forest models**, which remain largely similar.

Although this approach is not ideal, maintaining methodological consistency was prioritized by using similar configuration parameters across both datasets. This ensures comparability and allows us to learn from these two products to enhance Sentinel-2 cartography in the future. The only adjustment made was to the number of out-of-range observations required to confirm a change. This modification accounts for differences in image acquisition frequency: Landsat captures one image every 15 days for a given location, whereas Sentinel-2 acquires one every 5 days, with orbital overlap enabling up to two images per week.

In this case, the five **Landsat-derived** models at the national level were directly adopted, without conducting intermediate tests in the pilot provinces. Consequently, the model distribution remains as shown in **Figure 4**. The final configuration parameters used for **Sentinel-2** are provided in the following tables.

The table illustrates how the number of observations varied across provinces within the same model. This variation was due to significantly different behaviors among provinces within the same model, leading to higher noise levels in some areas. To address this, we opted to increase the number of observations. The reasons behind these differences in noise levels within the cartography require further investigation. In some cases, severe droughts have weakened forested areas, but these changes are not always detectable in high-resolution images during the assessment. Another contributing factor to noise is the presence of open-canopy forests, where variations in soil conditions, rather than vegetation, are the primary source of noise. In any case, further research is necessary to determine whether these are indeed the main causes or if other factors are at play.

Regarding the bands used for the classification model with Random Forest, as previously mentioned, they were the same as those used for Landsat and are presented in Tables 2 and 4.

Table 5. Algorithm Configuration Parameters for the New Models (Sentinel-2)

Province	Index	Change Magnitude Threshold	#Obs	Chi Square Probability	Min Num of Years	Lambda
Northern	NDVI, TCW, NBR	-2673	8	0.99	1.33	0.002
Northeastern	TCW	-141	12			
Southern	NBR	-131	24 and 30			
Central	NDVI	-743	8 and 15			
Eastern	NBR	-131	12 and 18			

2.6.2.1 Postprocessing

A sieve filter was applied to the resulting cartography to remove pixel groups smaller than or equal to 5 (0.45 ha) in Landsat and 13 (0.48 ha) in Sentinel-2. Additionally, a 7×7-pixel mode filter was implemented to minimize the salt-and-pepper effect in the classification, enhancing overall data consistency.

2.7 Quality Assessment and Results

2.7.1 Landsat Quality Assessment

While these national-scale maps will be validated using the reference database being developed within the framework of the FORWARDS project—following the established protocol to compare change detection results across different products—preliminary testing has been conducted to identify the optimal combination of parameters for both change detection and classification.

2.7.1.1 Pilot Provinces

The assessment of the **"Change" – "No Change" cartography (2017–2021)** was conducted using the reference database described in Section 2.5.1. This database enabled an assessment of the correspondence between observed points and the model's predictions. Based on this comparison, confusion matrices were generated to calculate standard accuracy metrics, including overall accuracy and omission and commission error rates for both classes.

A different approach was used to validate the **type-of-change cartography**. Changes recorded in 2022 by the Global Forest Change (GFC) product (Hansen et al., 2013) (see section 2.5.2) were compared against the generated cartography. Each GFC polygon was assigned the predominant class from the map, determined by the majority value within its area. Confusion matrices were then constructed to assess classification accuracy, calculating overall accuracy and specific error rates for each change class.

Figure 5. Distribution of photointerpreted points. Change-No Change (left), Based on type of change (right)

Table 6. Number of photointerpreted points for both cartographies

Province	#Photointerpreted points Change - No Change	#Photointerpreted points based on type of change
Asturias	50 - 166	180
Sevilla	48 - 508	270
Huesca	35 - 262	105

2.7.1.2 Additional Provinces

For the additional provinces, both the "Change"-"No Change" cartography and the classification-based cartography from the 2022 products were evaluated using a combination of random and stratified sampling. The selected points were photointerpreted using VHR imagery into one of these classes: "No Change", "Clear cut", "Thinning," "Shrubs Clearing," and "Wildfire, to generate confusion matrices and assess the models' accuracy.

Table 7. Distribution of photointerpreted points in additional provinces

Province	# Photointerpreted points
Barcelona	323
Bizkaia	113
Castellón	316
Girona	198
Lleida	203
Murcia	274
Navarra	246
Palencia	256
Segovia	217
Teruel	232

Figure 6. Distribution of photointerpreted points by change type in Bizkaia (2022). The color coding is as follows: Red represents forest fires; Dark green denotes clear-cuts; Light green indicates thinning; and Brown signifies shrubs clearing.

2.7.2 Landsat Results

2.7.2.1 Pilot Provinces

“Change” – “No Change” Cartography for the Period 2017–2021

Figure 7 presents the confusion matrices obtained for the three pilot provinces. Overall, the models demonstrated high global accuracy, exceeding 93%. However, commission errors, which represent the proportion of pixels incorrectly classified as “Change,” were high in all three cases, ranging from 19% to 27%, with particularly elevated values in the province of Huesca. This error is expected to decrease by increasing the minimum size of pixel groups to be filtered, which will help eliminate noise.

On the other hand, omission errors, which correspond to undetected change pixels, were relatively low in Asturias (12%) and Huesca (9%), while in Seville, this class exhibited a higher error rate, reaching 19%. In Seville, using 12 consecutive observations to identify an event as “Change” reduced the detection of actual changes. However, lowering this number to 6 or 9 observations significantly increased commission errors. Achieving a balance in Seville proved challenging, mainly due to the presence of lower-density forested areas, where soil effects considerably impact change detection.

Figure 7. Confusion matrices for quality assessment of 'Change' and 'No Change' (Pilot Provinces)

Another factor to consider regarding commission errors is that, upon closer analysis of the time series observations, significant changes in spectral response are often detected that are not apparent during the photointerpretation of high-resolution images. These non-visible changes could be attributed to minor clearings or forested areas undergoing early-stage decline, which remains imperceptible in higher-resolution imagery. Figure 8 illustrates an example of this phenomenon.

Figure 8. Example of a change identified by the CCDC algorithm in 2017, photointerpreted as "No Change." A) Area classified as change; B) Image from 2015; C) Image from 2017; D) Image from 2020. Bottom: Time series of observations and the change detected by the algorithm in 2017.

Cartography by Type of Change (2022)

The analysis of the confusion matrices reflects the performance of the three models developed to classify different types of change in Asturias, Huesca, and Seville. Each model performed differently depending on the local characteristics and the distribution of classes in each region.

Asturias							
Observed							
Map	Class	clear-cutting	thinning	bush clearing	wildfires	Total	Commission Error
		clear-cutting	139	2	5	2	148
	thinning	0	0	0	0	0	
	bush clearing	0	0	0	0	0	
	wildfires	2	1	18	11	32	0.66
	Total	141	3	23	13	180	
	Omission Error	0.01	1.00	1.00	0.15		
	Global Accuracy						0.83

Huesca							
Observed							
Map	Class	clear-cutting	thinning	bush clearing	wildfires	Total	Commission Error
		clear-cutting	15	2	0	2	19
	thinning	11	59	0	2	72	0.18
	bush clearing	0	0	0	0	0	
	wildfires	2	0	7	5	14	0.64
	Total	28	61	7	9	105	
	Omission Error	0.46	0.03	1.00	0.44		
	Global Accuracy						0.75

Sevilla							
Observed							
Map	Class	clear-cutting	thinning	bush clearing	wildfires	Total	Commission Error
		clear-cutting	3	1	0	0	4
	thinning	13	45	22	1	81	0.44
	bush clearing	14	25	118	0	157	0.25
	wildfires	10	2	15	1	28	0.96
	Total	40	73	155	2	270	
	Omission Error	0.93	0.38	0.24	0.50		
	Global Accuracy						0.62

Figure 9. Confusion matrices for quality assessment by type of change.

The imbalance in the quality assessment sample across the different types of change was due to variations in the forest conditions of the pilot provinces, where certain types of treatments are more prevalent. To address this, the training sample was expanded to include neighboring provinces or those with similar characteristics, aiming to increase the variability of change types represented in the training areas (Table 2).

In **Asturias**, the model achieved an overall accuracy of **83%**, with moderate precision and significant variations between classes. The “**clear-cut**” class was the best classified, showing very low commission and omission errors. However, the “**thinning**” and “**shrub clearing**” classes were not detected, with most **shrub clearing** events being misclassified as **wildfires**, leading to a high commission error for the fire class.

The model developed for **Huesca** obtained an overall accuracy of **75%**, but with uneven performance across classes. The “**clear-cut**” class had a **commission error of 0.21** and a **high omission error of 0.46**, indicating difficulties in consistently identifying this type of change. The “**thinning**” class was the best detected, with low commission and omission errors. As in Asturias, the “**shrub clearing**” class was not detected, highlighting the model's limitations in identifying this type of change. Additionally, the “**wildfire**” class also exhibited high commission and omission errors.

While the model performed well in detecting thinning, improvements are needed to enhance accuracy for **clear-cuts, shrub clearings, and fires**.

The model applied in **Seville** had the lowest overall accuracy (**62%**), with highly variable results across classes. Although it was more effective in identifying **shrub clearing**, its performance was limited for the other categories, particularly **clear-cuts and wildfires**.

Figure 10. Example of type-of-change cartography generated for Asturias (left), Huesca (center), and Seville (right) in 2022. Class representation: Red – forest fires; Dark green – clear-cuts; Light green – thinning; Brown – understory clearing.

2.7.2.2 Additional Provinces

The following table provides a summary of the results obtained after the assessment of both types of cartography for 2022.

Table 8. Summary of Quality Assessment Results

Province	Overall Accuracy (Change-No Change)	Overall Accuracy (Type of change)
Barcelona	0.92	0.7
Bizkaia	0.89	0.82
Castellón	0.94	0.78
Girona	0.91	0.86
Lleida	0.94	0.47
Murcia	0.93	0.77
Navarra	0.93	0.39
Palencia	0.91	0.83
Segovia	0.86	0.6
Teruel	0.92	0.49

2.7.3 Sentinel -2 Quality Assessment

In the case of Sentinel-2, quality assessment was initially performed visually in the pilot provinces. The generated change mapping was compared with the mapping derived from Landsat data, providing initial insights into key differences between the two products. **However, a more comprehensive and quantitative assessment will be conducted as part of Work Package 5 of this project.**

To more accurately determine the number of Sentinel-2 image observations required to classify an event as a real change in each model, the 2022 reference database outlined in Section 2.5.2 was used. The results, presented in the following section, along with visual quality control of the cartography produced for all years, facilitated the initial selection of parameters proposed for the first version of the Sentinel-2 cartography.

Following this intermediate assessment, it became evident that using fixed-year observations posed challenges in certain areas affected by prolonged drought. In 2023, some regions showed a higher number of detected changes, which may be attributed to noise caused by soil interference or subtle vegetation decline—phenomena not always easy to interpret in high-resolution imagery.

The following figure illustrates this issue with an example from northern Huelva province, showing detected changes in 2022 (left) versus 2023 (right), using 24 observations (top) and 30 observations (bottom). Increasing to 30 observations results in the loss of some real changes, which is more problematic in certain areas. However, this adjustment is the most viable approach to minimizing noise while preserving as many real changes as possible. Even with 30 observations, the noise is still visible; this issue requires further investigation.

Figure 11. Detected changes in the northern Huelva province: 2022 (left) vs. 2023 (right), with 24 observations (top) and 30 observations (bottom).

This led to variations in the number of observations used to detect changes in the different provinces within each of the 5 models created. Next figure presents the final configuration of observations for each province and year in the generated cartography.

Figure 12. Minimum number of consecutive observations required to confirm a change per province

2.7.4 Sentinel -2 Results

The results of the analysis to determine the most appropriate number of observations for detecting "Change" – "No Change" are presented below. For these analyses, the point database described in Section 2.5.2 was used. These results, along with visual review, helped us determine the final number of observations to be used in each province.

A more comprehensive and quantitative assessment will be carried out as part of Work Package 5 of this project, which will include both "Change" – "No Change" and "Type of Change" performance assessments.

The following tables summarize the results obtained for the additional provinces in the "Change" – "No Change" cartography for 2022, based on different numbers of observations.

Figure 13. Accuracy and Error Metrics for Change Detection Across Different Regions and different number of observations

3 Conclusions

This study successfully implemented a satellite-based methodology, utilizing Landsat and Sentinel-2 imagery, for national-scale forest disturbance monitoring across the Iberian Peninsula and the Balearic Islands. The CCDC algorithm, coupled with Random Forest classification, enabled automated and reproducible detection and categorization of various disturbance types, including thinning, clear cuts, scrub clearing, and wildfires.

While the Landsat-derived "Change" – "No Change" product achieved high overall accuracy (over 93%), commission errors, particularly in southern and eastern provinces characterized by sparse vegetation and severe drought years, necessitate further parameter adjustments and calibration. This issue is more pronounced in Sentinel-2 derived maps, requiring even more refined adjustments. Although "Type of Change" classification showed promising results for both Landsat and Sentinel-2, further improvements are needed.

The methodology's adaptability to regional forest characteristics facilitated the scaling of pilot-phase models to national coverage, demonstrating its effectiveness for large-scale monitoring. Sentinel-2's higher temporal and spatial resolution offers significant advantages, enabling earlier change detection compared to Landsat, thereby enhancing dynamic ecosystem monitoring. However, it also presents challenges, including increased noise and commission errors, requiring further evaluation.

This project establishes the feasibility and effectiveness of large-scale remote sensing for forest disturbance monitoring, while identifying key areas for refinement. These include optimizing change detection in ecosystems with sparse vegetation or adverse climatic conditions, expanding the classification system to encompass more disturbance types, and refining Sentinel-2 derived maps.

Furthermore, comprehensive validation is crucial to address commission errors and refine the methodology as new frequencies and data sources become available. To this end, Work Package 5 (WP5) will conduct a thorough validation of these products, revealing specific areas for improvement. Additionally, Work Package 4 (WP4) will explore product harmonization, aiming to resolve the observed challenges.

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